

MONICA 2025 SURVEY REPORT: COST-EFFECTIVE MONITORING OF BENTHIC COMMUNITIES ON THE CAP DE CREUS CONTINENTAL SHELF (NW MEDITERRANEAN)

Project MONICA - Application of novel cost-effective imaging tools for
the MONItoring of benthic ecosystems in the offshore marine area of CAP de Creus

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)
Grant agreement ID: 101154656

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CAP DE CREUS CONTINENTAL SHELF (NW MEDITERRANEAN)**

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CRUISE SUMMARY

A two-week survey to collect underwater video imagery was conducted in September 2025 on the continental shelf of Cap de Creus (NW Mediterranean), an area included within the limits of the Site of Community Importance (SCI) of the Natura 2000 network “*Sistema de cañones submarinos occidentales del Golfo de León*” (ESZZ16001). The video images were collected to evaluate, for the first time, potential changes in the composition and structure of shelf-dwelling benthic communities inside the SCI over the last 13-15 years. Seabed video footage was acquired using the cost-effective imaging system *Azor drift-cam*, deployed from a local fishing vessel and replicating ROV transects carried out between 2010 and 2012 during the *LIFE+ INDEMARES* project. Overall, 30 successful transects were performed at depths of 90-165 m, across different substrate types (mud, sand, gravels and outcropping rocks) and benthic communities (e.g., sea pens, soft corals, crinoids, gorgonians and cerianthids). The total length of seafloor that was surveyed reached 21 linear km, producing more than 24 hours of new seabed video footage. This survey also demonstrated the effectiveness of the low-cost underwater video system *Azor drift-cam* for surveying and monitoring circalittoral and bathyal habitats of the Mediterranean Sea from small local vessels.

BACKGROUND

In 2014, the offshore marine habitats of Cap de Creus (NE Spain) were included in the Site of Community Importance (SCI) “*Sistema de cañones submarinos occidentales del Golfo de León*” under the Habitats Directive (<https://eunis.eea.europa.eu/sites/ESZZ16001>). This marine area is characterized by a complex geological and oceanographic setting, mainly due to the proximity of the submarine canyon to the shoreline (Lastras et al., 2007). Owing to the narrowing of the continental shelf, cold waters from the Gulf of Lions are funneled through the canyon towards the deep basin, particularly during winter months, enhancing the transport of sediments and organic matter (Canals et al., 2006; Palanques et al., 2006; Puig et al., 2008). These oceanographic processes strongly influence the geological composition of the continental shelf, with muds and sands accumulating in the inner shelf, coarser sediments and bioclastic gravels towards the shelf edge, and rocky outcrops present in both the northern (90-100 m depth) and the southern sectors (100-120 m depth) (Lo Iacono et al., 2012).

The continental shelf and submarine canyon of Cap de Creus were ecologically characterized during the *LIFE+ INDEMARES* project (2008-2012; Gili et al., 2011; Dominguez-Carrió et al., 2014), with underwater video surveys revealing a diverse benthic ecosystem. The continental shelf provides habitat for sea pen and soft coral assemblages, gorgonian gardens, crinoid beds and sponge grounds (among others), while the submarine canyon hosts cold-water corals associated with oysters and brachiopods, as well as assemblages dominated by cerianthids and sea urchins (Dominguez-Carrió et al., 2022; Orejas et al., 2009). The marine area of Cap de Creus has been subject to both artisanal and commercial fishing activities for decades (Gómez-Mestres and Lloret, 2019; Demestre et al., 2015), with commercial bottom trawling having influenced the composition of benthic communities inhabiting soft-bottom areas of the shelf (de Juan et al., 2012; Dominguez-Carrió et al., 2022), and longline fishing leading to accumulations of abandoned lines on the canyon head, especially in areas with vertical walls and overhangs (Dominguez-Carrió et al., 2020).

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) requires EU Member States to monitor the evolution of the benthic ecosystems found inside Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) in order to assess whether conservation objectives are being met (Brown, 2017). Within this context, the MSCA project *MONICA* was formulated to explore the potential of low-cost underwater imaging systems to generate cost-effective data suitable for the monitoring of Cap de Creus offshore MPA, thereby supporting the management of its marine biodiversity.

MAIN OBJECTIVE

The main goal of the MONICA 2025 survey was to collect underwater imagery from the continental shelf of Cap de Creus (NW Mediterranean) to evaluate, for the first time, potential changes in the composition and structure of benthic communities occurring within the Site of Community Importance (SCI) “*Sistema de cañones submarinos occidentales del Golfo de León*”. Changes will be evaluated through comparisons with image data collected during the *LIFE+ INDEMARES* project (2010-2012). A secondary goal was to assess the applicability of the low-cost imaging system *Azor drift-cam*, deployed from small local vessels, for monitoring circalittoral and bathyal habitats of the Mediterranean Sea.

LOCATION

Site of Community Importance (SCI) of the Natura 2000 network “*Sistema de cañones submarinos occidentales del Golfo de León*” (ESZZ16001), NW Mediterranean.

VESSEL

Small-scale fishing vessel NOLL, based in the port of Llançà (Girona).

SURVEY DATES

30 August - 13 September 2025.

SCIENTIFIC TEAM (ICM-CSIC)

Carlos Dominguez-Carrió (chief scientist), Janire Salazar, Clémentine Mitoyen, Maria Pascual-Torner.

Figure 1. Scientific team that participated in the MONICA 2025 survey alongside the fishermen of the small-scale fishing vessel NOLL.

METHODOLOGY

Underwater video transects along the continental shelf were conducted using the cost-effective underwater camera system *Azor drift-cam* developed at the Institute of Marine Sciences - OKEANOS from the University of the Azores (see technical details in Dominguez-Carrió et al., 2021). The imaging system was deployed from a small-scale fishing vessel based in Llança (Girona), using its hydraulic winch to control the position of the camera system over the seabed (Figure 2). The video transects performed during the MONICA 2025 survey were planned to replicate the ROV transects carried out during the LIFE+ INDEMARES project (2009-2012). In each deployment, the vessel was left to drift following the path of the ROV dive, manually adjusting the position of the vessel to replicate the previous transect as accurately as possible (see examples in Figure 3). Dives were planned to last for approximately 45-60 minutes over the seafloor, with the system generally moving at speeds below 1 knot. Under favorable conditions, 3 to 5 dives were completed per working day, depending on transect length and distance from the coast.

Figure 2. Set up of the Azor drift-cam on board of the fishing vessel, with all the components connected and ready to be deployed.

Figure 3. Several examples of the paths conducted with the fishing vessel (blue lines) aiming to replicate the paths followed by ROVs during the LIFE+ INDEMARES project (yellow lines).

CRUISE STATISTICS

A total of 30 successful underwater video transects were performed with the *Azor drift-cam* over the continental shelf of Cap de Creus between the 2nd and the 12th of September 2025. Due to adverse weather conditions and fishing regulations, no sampling could be carried out during the 5th, 6th, 9th and 11th of September. Dives were carried out at depths between 90 and 165 m, over different substrate types (mud, sand, gravels, outcropping rocks) and benthic communities (sea pens and soft corals, crinoids, gorgonians, cerianthids). The sum of distances covered in all transects reached 21 km of seafloor and produced more than 24 hours of new video footage. The longest dive reached almost 1200 linear m, while the shortest dive just over 200 m. The geographical location of the different underwater dives along the continental shelf of Cap de Creus is shown in Figure 4, with metadata associated with each dive provided in Table 1.

Figure 4. Location of the underwater video transects performed with the *Azor drift-cam* on the continental shelf of Cap de Creus (NW Mediterranean) during the MONICA 2025 survey. Start-end positions, deployment times and start-end depths for each dive are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Metadata of the underwater transects performed with the Azor drift-cam on the continental shelf of Cap de Creus during the MONICA 2025 survey. St = Station; Lat. = Latitude (°N); Lon. = Longitude (°E). Dates given as dd/mm (all from 2025). Dive time is provided in hh:mm:ss. Stations marked with (*) were not considered valid due to several circumstances, including equipment failure, bad drift or bad visibility.

St	Date	Time at bottom	Time off bottom	Dive time	Start Lat.	Start Lon.	End Lat.	End Lon.	Dive length (m)	Start-end depth (m)
1*	02/09	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
2	02/09	12:49:01	13:41:13	0:52:12	42.385	3.290	42.377	3.287	910	106-109
3	02/09	14:29:46	15:21:17	0:51:31	42.389	3.312	42.385	3.301	940	150-110
4	02/09	15:49:16	17:00:10	1:10:54	42.401	3.300	42.399	3.289	940	164-109
5	03/09	8:14:55	9:11:02	0:56:07	42.364	3.314	42.366	3.321	590	117-119
6*	03/09	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
7	03/09	10:43:45	11:27:20	0:43:35	42.345	3.317	42.352	3.316	750	107-111
8	03/09	12:21:15	12:56:10	0:34:55	42.366	3.262	42.370	3.254	830	99-96
9*	04/09	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
10*	04/09	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
11	04/09	11:23:07	12:53:20	1:30:13	42.305	3.396	42.310	3.393	610	120-117
12	04/09	13:50:06	14:50:06	1:00:00	42.281	3.463	42.289	3.460	890	125-129
13	04/09	16:33:40	17:21:10	0:47:30	42.373	3.297	42.363	3.301	1060	109-112
14	04/09	18:01:44	18:40:30	0:38:46	42.385	3.271	42.379	3.272	670	103-104
15	07/09	8:41:38	9:45:35	1:03:57	42.389	3.257	42.395	3.255	710	99-98
16	07/09	10:20:29	11:35:30	1:15:01	42.353	3.276	42.361	3.276	880	97-103
17	07/09	11:58:15	12:45:00	0:46:45	42.350	3.289	42.353	3.290	370	98-103
18	08/09	10:31:12	11:09:23	0:38:11	42.413	3.254	42.408	3.253	490	99-98
19	08/09	11:50:07	13:01:49	1:11:42	42.369	3.279	42.370	3.286	610	105-110
20	08/09	14:02:48	14:51:40	0:48:52	42.308	3.365	42.303	3.363	580	117-109
21	08/09	15:07:52	16:03:55	0:56:03	42.305	3.354	42.296	3.361	1080	95-105
22	08/09	16:21:04	17:15:42	0:54:38	42.290	3.357	42.282	3.363	1060	99-105
23	08/09	17:37:18	17:59:53	0:22:35	42.300	3.367	42.296	3.364	530	118-108
24	10/09	14:01:48	14:29:51	0:28:03	42.339	3.317	42.345	3.307	1110	98-99
25	10/09	15:06:58	15:15:00	0:08:02	42.340	3.339	42.342	3.337	220	117-116
26	10/09	15:27:18	15:54:45	0:27:27	42.340	3.339	42.340	3.336	290	117-115
27	10/09	16:14:35	16:42:06	0:27:31	42.343	3.322	42.350	3.316	990	108-110
28	10/09	17:09:33	18:00:06	0:50:33	42.373	3.269	42.384	3.268	1190	101-102
29*	10/09	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
30	10/09	20:21:32	20:40:41	0:19:09	42.336	3.329	42.336	3.324	390	100-97
31*	10/09	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
32	12/09	11:15:08	11:55:54	0:40:46	42.393	3.288	42.391	3.287	260	107-107
33	12/09	12:22:10	13:52:40	1:30:30	42.391	3.293	42.388	3.293	300	106-108
34	12/09	14:57:30	15:44:10	0:46:40	42.281	3.342	42.283	3.334	650	93-89
35	12/09	16:11:39	17:09:44	0:58:05	42.263	3.383	42.269	3.379	690	121-121
36	12/09	17:58:07	19:01:25	1:03:18	42.341	3.307	42.348	3.3101	830	93-115

CRUISE DIARY

2nd September 2025

We left harbour at 08:00 AM to carry out the first deployment as a test dive. We searched for a flat and sandy area close to the port, at a depth of approximately 80 m. When the system was deployed, the live-view feed on board of the vessel started showing a series of interferences on the screen, which increased as we descended through the water column, preventing a safe navigation. The system was rapidly recovered to avoid further issues. After

some tests, the problem was identified in one of the vessel's 220V sockets, which produced interferences. Luckily, they disappeared after changing all the electrical connections to a different socket. The system was then deployed again at the same location, this time with improved image quality when it reached the seabed. After completing the test dive, we moved towards the submarine canyon, where we performed 3 transects, one on the northern continental shelf (St. 2; Figure 4) and two on the shelf break (St. 3-4; Figure 4), covering depths between 105 and 165 m. Only sparse benthic fauna was observed in these dives, characteristic of soft bottom habitats of the shelf break such as soft corals, holothurians and sea urchins. Those 3 dives generated almost 3 hours of video footage, covering nearly 3 km of seabed (Table 1). We returned to port at 6:00 PM.

3rd September 2025

We set off at 07:00 AM to maximize the amount of time at sea ahead of the weather forecast for the day. We completed 3 additional transects on the northern continental shelf at depths between 95 and 120 m. Two dives (St. 5, St. 8; Figure 4) were performed in areas dominated by pennatulaceans and soft corals (see Figure 7a-c for examples), while St. 7 (Figure 4) was carried out in an area of coral gardens dominated by the gorgonian *Eunicella cavolini* and the sponge *Suberites syringella* (see Figure 7g-i for examples). These 3 dives generated more than 2 hours of video footage, covering nearly 2 km of seabed (Table 1). We had to return to port at 2:00 PM after the southern winds started to increase, as sea conditions made it difficult to safely operate the system.

4th September 2025

We left the harbour at 08:00 AM, heading towards the southern continental shelf, where we carried out two transects targeting the sponge grounds identified in Dominguez-Carrió et al. (2022), at depths of 115-130 m (St.11-12; Figure 4). At around 2:00 PM, the southern winds started to pick up, with sea conditions making it difficult to operate the *Azor drift-cam*. We headed North, where sea conditions were much better due to the shelter provided by the cape. We completed two more transects on the northern continental shelf, one over an area of pennatulaceans and soft corals (St.13; ~110 m depth) and another over a crinoid aggregation of the species *Leptometra phalangium* (St. 14; ~100 m depth; see examples in Figure 7e-f). During St. 13, some water leaked into one of the cylinders containing the LED lights, burning the connections. For this reason, we had to complete the last dive of the day with only one LED light functioning correctly. The 4 dives of the day generated almost 4 hours of video footage, covering 3.2 km of seabed (Table 1). We returned to port at 7:00 PM.

Figure 5. Selected images of the scientific team operating the Azor drift-cam on board of the fishing vessel NOLL during the first 3 days of the survey (4-7 September).

5th-6th September 2025

We stayed on land both days. On Friday 5th, the northern Tramuntana winds blew too strongly to allow any work at sea (see weather forecast in Figure 6). We stayed in Llançà fixing the damaged equipment and processing the data generated the previous day. On Saturday 6th we remained on land due to the impossibility of operating at sea because of fishing regulations and we continued working on the processing of the data generated.

7th September 2025

We left harbour at 07:00 AM, conducting 3 video transects on the northern shelf. The first dive (St. 15; Figure 4) surveyed an area of muds and sands with pennatulaceans and soft corals, while the other two dives targeted gorgonian populations at depths of 95-105 m (St. 16-17, Figure 4). The 3 dives of the day generated almost 3 hours of video footage, covering nearly 2 km of seabed (Table 1). We returned back to port at 1:30 PM.

8th September 2025

Sea conditions remained difficult at the start of the day because of the wind that blew the previous day. For this reason, we postponed the departure from port until 9:30 AM to operate in better sea conditions. Although there was some swell during the first hours of sampling, we carried out two dives off the coast of Llançà, at ~100 m depth (St. 18-19; Figure 4). Around 01:00 PM, once the sea had calmed down, we headed out to the southern continental shelf, where we carried out 4 more dives, covering depths of 95-120 m depth (St. 20-23; Figure 4). These dives were done in areas with a mixture of mud, and small bioclastic gravels

dominated by pennatulaceans and soft corals. The total amount of video footage generated throughout the day totaled almost 5 hours, covering over 4 km of seabed (Table 1). We began heading back at 06:00 PM, with the northern winds picking up as we sailed towards port, arriving at 7:30 PM.

Figure 6. General weather forecast for Friday 5th (left) and Tuesday 8th September (right), showcasing the strength of the northern Tramuntana winds blowing in Cap de Creus. Arrows represent wind direction and numbers wind intensity in the Beaufort scale. Forecast from www.meteo.cat.

9th September 2025

We stayed in Llançà due to the strong Tramuntana winds that blew throughout the day (see weather forecast in Figure 6). We worked towards the processing of the data generated on previous days.

10th September 2025

The northern Tramuntana winds still blew during the first hours of the day, with a significant reduction in wind speed forecasted for lunch. We set sail at 01:00 PM, aiming to make the most of the favorable conditions expected for the afternoon. We conducted 7 video transects on the northern shelf (St. 24-28; St. 30; Figure 4), heading back to land at sunset. Two stations (St. 24, St. 30) were performed over the coral gardens dominated by *E. cavolini*, where high densities of octocorals and sponges were observed. The remaining dives surveyed areas with a mixture of mud and small bioclastic gravels, dominated by pennatulaceans and soft corals. The laser system showed some malfunction throughout the day, with one of the lasers not visible in some of the transects. The 7 dives of the day generated over 2.5 hours of video footage, covering approximately 4 km of seabed (Table 1).

Figure 7. Images of the benthic communities observed during the MONICA 2025 survey on the continental shelf of Cap de Creus recorded with the Azor drift-cam. (a-c) Soft corals of the species *Alcyonium palmatum* and sea pens of the species *Pteroeides griseum*. (d) Soft corals and a crinoid of the species *Leptometra phalangium*. (e-f) Aggregations of crinoids of the species *Leptometra phalangium*. (g-i) Coral gardens with the gorgonian *Eunicella cavolini* and the reptant sponge *Suberites syringella*. (j-k) The sea cucumber *Parastichopus regalis* over mixed substrates. (l) Areas of bioclastic deposits of the shelf break.

11th September 2025

We had to stay on land due to the restrictions imposed on fishing activities by the festivity of the Catalan National Day.

12th September 2025

Due to the northern Tramuntana winds that blew during the previous night, we could only head out to sea at around 10:00 AM, when sea conditions improved enough to safely operate the system. We performed 2 transects on the northern shelf while the swell was still relatively high (St. 32-33; Figure 4). Once the sea calmed down, we transited towards the southern shelf to carry out 2 more transects, one on a trawled area in front of Cadaqués (St. 34) and the other dive about two miles further away (St. 35), in an area identified as *Lanice*

conchilega community by Dominguez-Carrió et al. (2022). On the way back to port, we carried out one last dive (St. 36) over the *E. cavolini* aggregations (see examples of this community in Figure 7g-i), on the northern side of the cape. The laser system continued malfunctioning, and one of the lasers was not visible in some transects. The 5 dives of the day generated almost 5 hours of video footage, covering approximately 2.7 km of seabed (Table 1). We arrived at port at around 08:00 PM.

Figure 8. Selected images of the scientific team operating the Azor drift-cam on board of the fishing vessel NOLL during the last days of the survey (8-12 September).

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